

Complexo-titrimetric Estimation of Thallium(III) using Thiosemicarbazide as Replacing Reagent

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A simple and selective complexo-titrimetric method using the masking and demasking techniques is proposed for the determination of thallium(III). In presence of diverse metal ions thallium(III) is complexed with a known excess of EDTA and the uncomplexed EDTA is back titrated (pH 5-6, hexamine) with lead nitrate solution, using xylenol orange as indicator. Thiosemicarbazide solution in water is then added and the mixture heated on water bath for 2-5 min (45-50°) to displace all EDTA from the Tl-EDTA complex (in cold, 30-40 min is required). The freed EDTA is titrated against lead nitrate solution. Reproducible and accurate results are obtained in the concentration range 10-45 mg of thallium with relative error of <0.5% and standard deviation of <0.04.

RECENTLY, complexometric titrations, particularly those involving masking and demasking technique are receiving considerable attention in analysis for the simple reason that they provide more selective, accurate and rapid methods for the determination of the desired metal ion in the presence of associated metal ions. Literature survey reveals that although there are reagents like $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, ascorbic acid¹, diethylenetriamine-*N,N,N',N',N''*-pentaacetic acid² etc. that are suitable for direct complexometric titration of Tl^{III} , complexometric determination of Tl^{III} using demasking technique is seldom tried. Thiopyrin³ is one such reagent used in chelatometric titration of Tl^{III} using replacing reagents. Complexometric determination of Tl^{III} using thiosemicarbazide as a replacing reagent is therefore attempted with success and the results reported herein.

Experimental

Thiosemicarbazide (A.R.) was used as a 1% solution in water. Thallous nitrate solution was prepared from thallic nitrate (A.R.) following the reported procedure⁴ and standardised by chromate method⁵. A 0.02 M lead nitrate solution was prepared from an analytical grade sample and standardised by salicylaldehyde method⁶. EDTA solution (0.04 M) was prepared by dissolving the disodium salt of EDTA in distilled water. A 0.05% aqueous solution of xylenol orange indicator was prepared.

Procedure: To an aliquot of acidic solution of the sample containing 10-45 mg of Tl^{III} , an excess of 0.04 M EDTA solution was added. The solution was diluted to 30-40 ml with distilled water followed by solid hexamine to adjust the pH to 5-6. The excess EDTA was titrated against

standard lead nitrate solution to a sharp colour change of xylenol orange from yellow to pink. A 1% solution of thiosemicarbazide in water was then added, the reaction mixture heated on a water-bath for 2-5 min, cooled to room temperature and the released EDTA titrated against the lead nitrate solution as before. The second titre value corresponds to thallium present in the aliquot.

Analysis of thallium complexes: Thallium(I) complexes were prepared from some sulphur donor ligands by conventional methods and their purity was checked from elemental analysis. The complex (~0.2-0.3 g) was decomposed by evaporation to near-dryness with aqua regia. The residue was then cooled, dissolved in 2 N HNO_3 (3 ml) and made up to 100 ml with distilled water. Aliquots of 10 ml were used for titration as per the proposed procedure.

Results and Discussion

Effect of excess of thiosemicarbazide: Experimental results show that a little excess of thiosemicarbazide over the stoichiometric ratio of 1:1 for the metal to the reagent is desirable. However, no adverse effects were observed even on adding larger excess of the reagent.

Effect of heat: The displacement of EDTA from the Tl-EDTA complex by thiosemicarbazide at room temperature is rather slow taking 25-30 min. Quantitative release of the EDTA takes place when the reaction mixture is heated on a water-bath for 2-5 min before the second titration.

Accuracy and precision: To check the accuracy and precision of the method, determinations of thallium were carried out under optimised conditions. The results (Table 1) indicate that the method is accurate as well as precise.

TABLE 1—PRECISION AND ACCURACY IN DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM(III)

Tl taken mg	Tl found mg	Standard deviation	Recovery* %
9.184	9.213	0.04	100.31
18.367	18.414	0.00	100.26
27.561	27.564	0.03	100.05
36.734	36.731	0.03	99.99
45.918	46.038	0.03	100.26

* Average of five determinations.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of co-ions on the accuracy and precision of the method for Tl^{III} was studied by estimating 18.367 mg of Tl^{III} in presence of each of these cations. The results relating to non-interfering cations are summarised in Table 2. It may be noted that cations like Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Fe^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Bi^{III} and Al^{III} severely interfere. Consequently, Tl^{III} can not be estimated by this method in presence of these cations.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE METAL IONS

Tl present in solution = 18.367 mg				
Metal ion	Concn. level mg	Tl found* mg	Mean	Recovery %
Zn ^{II}	10	18.366	18.366	99.99
	100	18.366		
Cd ^{II}	32	18.374	18.457	100.49
	64	18.539		
Ni ^{II}	12	18.966	18.292	99.59
	30	18.217		
Mn ^{II}	6	18.966	18.292	99.59
	120	18.217		
Co ^{II}	12	18.539	18.452	100.46
	30	18.965		
Fe ^{III}	12	18.367	18.441	100.40
	30	18.514		
Au ^{III}	4	18.292	18.292	99.59
	16	18.292		

* Average of 9 determinations.

Applications : The usefulness of the proposed method lies in the fact that it can be successfully applied for the determination of thallium in its complexes with sulphur containing ligands and also in the mixture of salts of Tl^{III}. It can also be used for the determination of the composition of alloys containing Tl. The results are summarised in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3—ANALYSIS OF THALLIUM COMPLEXES

Compd.	Tl present %	Tl found %
Tl(C ₄ H ₄ N ₄ S) ^a	61.30	61.34
Tl(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ^b	46.51	46.52

^aThallium complex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole. ^bThallium complex of 3-(*o*-oresyloxymethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM IN ARTIFICIAL MIXTURES

Tl present in the solution = 18.367 mg			
Metal ions	Quantity added mg	Tl found* mg	Recovery %
Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	10 + 64	18.421	100.29
Zn ^{II} + Ni ^{II}	10 + 12	18.291	99.58
Zn ^{II} + Mn ^{II}	10 + 60	18.310	99.68
Zn ^{II} + Co ^{II}	55 + 12	18.390	100.13

* Average of 4 determinations.

Mechanism of demasking : Of the many possible mechanisms of demasking of metal-EDTA complexes, the one involving change in the oxidation state of the metal ion seems to be more plausible. Some metal ions form stable complexes with EDTA in their higher oxidation states, like +2 and +3, but not in +1 state. Thallium is one such metal in that it forms a stable complex⁷ with EDTA in +3 state (log *K* = 22.5) and shows little tendency for complexation in +1 state. Even if Tl^I forms a complex with EDTA it may do so only under high pH conditions (pH 8-9), but complete decomposition of the Tl^I-EDTA complex takes place under low pH conditions (pH 5-6). Therefore, the redox behaviour of Tl^I-Tl^{III} in acidic medium can be conveniently employed for the complexometric determination of Tl. Thiosemicarbazide is a powerful reducing agent in both acidic and basic media and is also a good complexing agent. In the acidic medium as employed in the present work, effective reduction of Tl^{III} to Tl^I takes place by a 10-electron change. The reactions involved are likely to be

SO₃ evolved from the solution is noticeable from the turning of K₂Cr₂O₇ paper green. The solution is tested for the presence of ammonia which is confirmed using Nessler's reagent.

Besides changing the oxidation state of thallium, thiosemicarbazide complexes with the Tl^I so formed and releases the previously complexed EDTA quantitatively. The +1 oxidation state of thallium in its complex was further confirmed by spot-test technique⁸. A red precipitate was formed when the solution of the complex in dilute hydrochloric acid was treated with one drop each of bismuth nitrate and sodium iodide. This result confirmed the +1 oxidation state of thallium in the solution. The cause for the slow displacement of EDTA from Tl-EDTA complex by thiosemicarbazide could now be traced to the slow rate of reduction in the cold. It is logical to expect that the rate increases on heating.

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